

Prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescents in a selected school, Thiruvananthapuram

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Abstract

Gaining independence from various restriction set by parents is overjoy for adolescent. However, it does not always happen as it planned. The current study was aimed to assess "Prevalence of Helicopter parenting among adolescents" in a selected school, Thiruvananthapuram. The objectives of the study were to assess the prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among adolescents, to assess the prevalence of Helicopter Parenting of fathers of adolescents, to assess the prevalence of Helicopter Parenting of mothers of adolescents, to find out the association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting of father's and selected socio-personal variables and to find out the association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting of mother's and selected socio-personal variables. The sample size consists of 209 adolescents in a selected school Thiruvananthapuram. The tool used was structured questionnaire with 2 sections, section A consists of socio-personal variables such as age, gender, class of study, birth order, religion, place of residence, annual income, occupation of mother and father, parenting style of mother and father and section B consists of standardized Helicopter Parenting Instrument which consists of 15 statements that is rated by a 5-point Likert scale. The data was analyzed with descriptive and inferential statistics by using SPSS. The result of the present study revealed that there is moderate prevalence of helicopter parenting practice in adolescents. Both parents exhibit helicopter parenting behavior and among that, majority of fathers (74.6%) showed helicopter parenting styles than the mothers (74.2%).

Keywords: Prevalence of Helicopter Parenting; Helicopter Parenting Instrument; Adolescent; SPSS

1. Introduction

1.1. "A lot of parents will do anything for their kids except let them be themselves"

India is a country where families follow patriarchal ideology and Indian family is closely knit unit where the parents play very important role. Indian parenting is value-based parenting. It is a fact that there are no universal rules in parenting styles. Different parenting styles have different impacts on kids. Each parents have unique style of parenting which they develop from their behavioral pattern and from the environment they have been grown up [1].

Parenting style of Indians has been Helicopter Parenting through ages. This is deep rooted in our society and culture as well. Helicopter parenting refers to a style of parenting where parents are overly focused on children and hovering around their children to protect them and make them succeed in their life. These over protective parents are deciding the future plans of their children without teaching and demonstrating adequate skills, to make them independent [2].

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The 'helicopter parenting' was first coined in 1990 (Cline and Fay,2020) that describes parents who 'hover' over their children. According to Hirsch and Goldberg helicopter parenting is a process of distinctive parenting that never allowed their children to make mistakes and trapped them in the cave of stress. It is a unique form of parenting style that is generally described as highly intensive and highly involved with their children [3].

A systemic review was done in Norway in 2022 regarding helicopter parenting and its relationship with depression and anxiety. The purpose of study was to assess the relationship between helicopter parenting and symptoms of anxiety and depression. They reviewed 38 eligible research articles and the study quality was assessed in accordance with Campbells Validity Typology. Majority of the studies included in this systematic review found a direct relationship between helicopter parenting and symptoms of anxiety and depression in children [4].

A study was done in 2020 to assess "Do Indians follow helicopter parenting" by Neelanjana Bose reported that, helicopter parents do keep a track on their child's development and progress in social, educational and interpersonal developments and ensure that the child is a part with others, in this competitive World. The study result showed that helicopter parenting is acceptable up to some level in guiding children but in long term neither is it useful nor advisable for the children because it creates anxiety and self- doubt in children as they lose confidence to do their own work with freedom [1].

Majority of the studies showed a direct relationship between helicopter parenting and symptoms of anxiety and depression. It is a well-established fact that helicopter parenting has psychological impacts on children and therefore, assessing the prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescents can provide insights into the need for modifying parenting styles

2. Material and methods

2.1. Hypothesis

- H0: There is no significant association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescent and selected socio-personal variables such as age, gender, birth order, religion, class of study, type of family, place of residence, monthly income, occupation of father occupation of mother, parenting style of father, parenting style of mother.
- H1: There is a significant association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescent and selected socio-personal variables such as age, gender, birth order, religion, class of study, type of family, place of residence, monthly income, occupation of father, occupation of mother, parenting style of father, parenting style of mother.

2.2. Research Approach

Quantitative research approach

2.3. Research Design

Descriptive non experimental research design

2.4. Setting of the study

The study was conducted in a selected Higher Secondary school, Thiruvananthapuram

2.5. Population

- Target population: Adolescent
- Accessible population: Adolescents who are studying in eleventh and twelfth standard of a selected Higher Secondary School, Thiruvananthapuram

2.6. Sample

Adolescents that include both boys and girls who are in the age group of 16-18 years studying in eleventh and twelfth standard of a selected Higher Secondary School, Thiruvananthapuram who meets the inclusion criteria.

2.7. Sample size

The sample consists of 209 adolescents' children

2.8. Sampling technique

Non-probability purposive sampling technique was used

2.9. Criteria for sampling technique

2.9.1. Inclusion criteria

- Adolescents within the age group of 16-18 years
- Adolescents who can read and write Malayalam and English

2.9.2. Exclusion criteria

- Adolescents who were not willing to participate in the study
- Adolescents who were not present at the time of data collection
- Adolescents those who have single parent

2.10. Research tool

Structured standardized questionnaire to assess prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescents which consist of two sections.

2.10.1. Section A

Socio-personal variables such as age, gender, birth order, religion, class of study, type of family, place of residence, monthly income, occupation of mother, occupation of father, parenting style of father and parenting style of mother

2.10.2. Section B

Helicopter Parenting Instrument which consists of 15 statements for both father and mother that are rated in a 5-point Likert Scale to assess the prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescents

2.11. Scoring

For each statement the maximum score given was 75 and the minimum score was 15. 5-point Likert scale was used with, strongly agree-5, agree -4, neutral -3, disagree -2, strongly disagree -1 for scoring of each statement for both father and mother and the scoring was done separately for each parent. The total scoring was done as follows:

Table 1 Scoring of Helicopter Parenting Instrument

Prevalence	Score
High	39-75
Moderate	38-55
Low	15-37

2.12. Pilot study

The Pilot study was conducted among 10% of the sample at selected higher secondary school, Thiruvananthapuram

2.13. Data collection procedure

Data collection was for a period of 1 month. The researchers went to the school on the day of data collection, and samples were selected using non-probability purposive sampling technique. Helicopter parenting Instruments was given to the samples who met the inclusion criteria and the response were analyzed

2.14. Plan for data analysis

The data was collected from 209 samples using descriptive and inferential statistics.

- Descriptive statistics: In the present study, frequency and percentage were used to analyze the socio-personal variables
- Inferential statistics: In this study, Chi-Square was used to analyze the association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among adolescents and selected socio-personal variables.

The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, (SPSS) software, IBM SPSS version 20

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Organization of study findings

The data were analyzed under the following headings

- Section A: Distribution of samples based on socio- personal variables
- Section B: Prevalence of helicopter parenting among mothers of adolescents
- Section C: Prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers of adolescents
- Section D: Association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers and selected socio personal variables such as age, gender, class of study, birth order, religion, type of family, place of residence, annual monthly income, occupation of father, parenting styles of father
- Section E: Association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among mothers and selected socio personal variables such as age, gender, class of study, birth order, religion, type of family, place of residence, annual monthly income, occupation of mother, parenting styles of mother

3.1.1. Section A: Distribution of samples based on socio personal variables

- Age: Out of 209 subjects 24.90% were 17 years, 53.60% were 18 years, and 21.50% were 19 years

Figure 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to age

- Gender: Majority of the samples were boys 59.8% and 40.2% were girls

Figure 2 Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to their gender

- Class of study: 47.40% of subjects were class XI and 52.60% of subjects were class XII

Figure 3 Percentage distribution of subjects according to their classes

- Birth order: 61.20% were first child, 35.40% were second child, and 3.30% were third and more

Figure 4 Percentage distribution of subjects according to birth order

- Religion: Majority, 74.60% belongs to Hindu, 21.10% belongs to Muslim, and 4.30% belongs to Christian communities

Figure 5 Percentage distribution of samples according to religion

- Place of residence: 43.50% belongs to rural area, 14.40% belongs to urban area, 42.10% belongs to semi-urban area respectively

Figure 6 Percentage distribution of subjects based on place of residence

- Type of family: Majority, 75.10% belongs to nuclear family, 22% belongs to joint family, and 2.90% belongs to extended family

Figure 7 Percentage distribution of subject based on type of family

- Annual income of family: Results shows that out of 209 subjects, 13.40% belongs to annual income below 20000 Rs/-, 67.50% belongs to annual income 20000 – 100000 Rs/- and 19.10% belongs to annual income above 100000 Rs/- respectively

Figure 8 Percentage distribution of subject based on annual income of family

- Occupation of mother: Majority of the mothers, 58.90% were jobless, 15.30% were Govt. employees, and 25.80% were private /self-employees respectively

Figure 9 Percentage distribution of subjects based on occupation of mother

- Occupation of father: 20.60% were govt employee, 78% were private/self-employed, 1.40% were jobless

Figure 10 Percentage distribution of subjects based on occupation of father

Parenting style of father: 37.30% were overprotective, 62.20% were liberal, and 0.50% were uninvolved

Figure 11 Percentage distribution of subjects based on parenting style of father

- Parenting style of mother: 26.30% were overprotective, 70.30% were liberal, and 3.30% were uninvolved

Figure 12 Percentage distribution of subjects based on parenting style of mother

3.1.2. Section B: Prevalence of helicopter parenting among mothers of adolescents

Table 2 Frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to prevalence of Helicopter Parenting of mothers (n=209)

SN.	Category	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
1	High (56-75)	44	21.1%
2	Moderate (38-55)	155	74.2%
3	Low (15-37)	10	4.8%

Table 1 reveals that majority 155 (74.2%) of mothers shows moderate prevalence of helicopter parenting

3.1.3. Section C: Prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers of adolescents

Table 3 Frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to prevalence of Helicopter Parenting of fathers (n=209)

SN.	Category	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
1	High (56-75)	34	16.3%
2	Moderate (38-55)	156	74.6%
3	Low (15-37)	19	9.1%

Table 2 reveals that majority 156 (74.6%) of fathers shows moderate prevalence of helicopter parenting

3.1.4. Section D: Association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers and selected socio personal variables such as age, gender, birth order, religion, type of family, place of residence, annual monthly income, occupation of father, parenting styles of father

Table 4 Chi square showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers with age` (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Age						
16	52	10	38	4	2	*38.938
17	112	17	85	10		
18	45	7	33	5		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 3 showed that there is statistically significant association between age and prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers. Calculated value (38.938) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 5 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among father with gender (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Gender						
Girl	84	18	61	5	1	*8.043
Boy	125	16	95	14		

*Significant at 0.05 Table 4 showed that there is statistically significant association between gender and prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers. Calculated value (8.043) is greater than tabulated value (3.84). Hence H1 is accepted.

Table 6 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among father with birth order (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Birth order						
First child	128	24	91	13	2	*105.483
Second child	74	9	59	6		
Third and more	7	1	6	0		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 5 shows that there is statistically significant association between birth order and prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers. Calculated value (105.483) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 7 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among father with religion (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Religion						
Hindu	156	28	112	16	2	*169.273
Muslim	44	6	36	2		
Christian	9	0	8	1		

* Significant at 0.05; Table 6 shows that there is statistically significant association between religion and prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers. Calculated value (169.273) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 8 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among father with place of residence (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Place of residence						
Rural	91	12	74	5	2	*33.943
Urban	30	5	19	6		
Semi urban	88	17	63	8		

* Significant at 0.05; Table 7 shows that there is statistically significant association between place of residence and prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers. Calculated value (33.943) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 9 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among father with type of family (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Type of family						
Joint family	46	5	38	3	2	*175.703
Nuclear family	157	29	114	14		
Extended family	6	0	4	2		

* Significant at 0.05; Table 8 shows that there is statistically significant association between type of family and prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers. Calculated value (175.703) is greater than tabulated value. Hence H1 is accepted

Table 10 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers with annual income of family (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Annual income of family						
Below 20000/-	28	3	19	6	2	*110.593
20000-100000/-	141	24	107	10		
Above 100000/-	40	7	30	3		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 9 shows that there is statistically significant association between annual income of family and prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers. Calculated value (110.593) is greater than (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 11 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among father with occupation of father (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Occupation of father						
Govt employee	42	8	28	6	2	*202.517
Private/Self Employed	164	25	127	12		
Jobless	3	1	1	1		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 10 shows that there is statistically significant association between occupation of father and prevalence of helicopter parenting. Calculated value (202.517) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 12 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among father with parenting style of father (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Parenting style of father						
Overprotective	55	17	34	4	2	*145.301
Liberal	147	17	117	13		
Uninvolved	7	0	5	2		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 11 shows that there is statistically significant association between parenting style of father and prevalence of Helicopter Parenting among fathers. Calculated value (145.301) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

3.1.5. Section E: Association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among mothers and selected socio personal variables such as occupation of mother and parenting styles of mother

Table 13 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among mother with occupation of mother (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Occupation of mother						
Govt employee	32	8	21	3	2	*64.718
Private/ Self employed	54	16	36	2		
Jobless	123	20	98	5		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 12 shows that there is statistically significant association between occupation of mother and prevalence of Helicopter Parenting. Calculated value (64.718) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

Table 14 Chi square value showing association between prevalence of helicopter parenting among mother with parenting style of mother (n=209)

Variables	Frequency	Prevalence			Degree of freedom(df)	Chi-square value(χ^2)
		High	Moderate	Low		
Parenting style of mother						
Overprotective	78	25	51	2	2	*120.928
Liberal	130	19	103	8		
Uninvolved	1	0	1	0		

*Significant at 0.05; Table 13 shows that there is statistically significant association between parenting style of mother and prevalence of helicopter parenting. Calculated value (120.928) is greater than tabulated value (5.99). Hence H1 is accepted

4. Conclusion

Helicopter parenting is the one of the trend parenting styles. The study findings revealed that there is still moderate prevalence of helicopter parenting among fathers and mothers of adolescents. Majority of fathers (74.6%) showed helicopter parenting styles than the mothers (74.2%). The findings highlight the need for intensive health teaching to father and mother regarding impact of helicopter parenting among adolescents

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The ethical clearance of this study was obtained from institutional Ethical Committee (IEC).

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in this study.

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